

D1.4

Applicability of the Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI to the COLLABS approach

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Executive Summary

This document was requested by the EC further to the deliverables promised by the project in its technical annex. Therefore, it is an assessment of the ethical use of AI technologies within the COLLABS project. The document contains a questionnaire filled in by project partners involved in AI activities, either as AI tools producers or as AI tools users.

Beware that this document does not aim to be complete in any sense nor give any definite answers to all questions of the questionnaire, as the project is in progress and much work remains to be done. Thus, the project gives the best of its knowledge about the topic of ethical use of AI techniques within COLLABS.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable examines the applicability of the EC Ethics Guidelines for trustworthy AI to the COLLABS project [1]. It has been required by the EC as an upfront work at M12. Thus, the COLLABS project provides the project's position on Ethics of AI tools without a complete development or use of the AI tools envisaged in the project DoA. The information given below is the best of our knowledge on Ethics, given our current project status. It may evolve once developments have been done.

The core of this document is located in chapter 3 that performs an assessment of these guidelines by using the assessment list defined in chapter III of [1]. It is preceded by chapter 2 that describes the AI tools developed and/or used in the project, such that the reader can put the questionnaire into the project perspectives. Chapter 4 terminates the deliverable with some conclusions.

2. Context - AI tools in COLLABS

This section describes the different AI tools developed and/or available in the project. It gives the reader some background information about the AI tools mentioned in section 3 below.

2.1.1 AI tool #1: Security Infusion (ITML)

2.1.1 Short description of tool

This component is an agent-based software, which collects, analyzes, visualizes, and presents real time and historical data that concern the operation and security status of an organization's IT resources, along with storing historical data from past logs and events to be used and analyzed later. The agents can be installed within Linux or Windows OS, while the managers reside in the cloud. Security infusion functions as a SIEM (security information and event management), monitoring, an IDS service. Basically, data from the underlying IVT infrastructure related with performance, services, network, and computing events, are monitored, collected, and analyzed in real time, with the capability of further storage for the purposes of incident investigation and forensic analysis. The software is mainly a cloud native application with an edge deployment option-if required.

2.1.2 Technologies used by the tool

The service will consist of three sub-tools; the Infusion Agents, the Infusion Manager (Field gateway or Cloud based), and the Infusion Web Interface. The technologies comprising the submodules of Security Infusion are delivered via Kubernetes and Docker and are comprised by a plethora of toolsets / frameworks like Laravel, Java SDK, Nginx, and modules from the Elastic stack.

2.1.3 Background of the tool

Security infusion is an in-house developed tool.

2.1.4 Development/deployment timeline in the project

Security infusion is the main tool for WP5, making it present throughout the lifecycle of the work package from the first deployment of the initial MVP (M8), until the end of the project.

2.1.5 *Link to demonstrators (in WP6)*

Since WP6 builds directly upon the outputs of WP5, security infusion will be taking part in most demonstrators.

2.1.6 *Expected TRL level of the tool at the end of the project and prospective use after COLLABS*

It will reach TRL level 8 and expected to be used commercially as an individual solution or within the overall integrated solution which is developed within COLLABS.

2.2 *AI tool #2: 3ACES (ITML)*

2.2.1 *Short description of tool*

This component is a software which applies data analysis as a service feature to support decision making in business environments. It is an embedded assistant that acts as a data analyst, hides the complexity of blending heterogeneous data streams and provides an automated preliminary analysis on the raw data. The first step for any business entity that wants to extract business value from their existing digital footprint through the use of 3ACES is to review the currently available data; examples of such data include but are not limited to online sales data, web usage, site analytics, production line sensors, logistics and warehouse data or existing market analysis. The second step is to collect the data, starting with a small representative sample and feed it to the 3ACES bot. A data scientist can optionally assist in this process in cases of enterprises that have vast amount of data from heterogeneous sources. Following the engagement of 3ACES bot, the data is processed and analyzed, in order to provide on-demand, self-service analytics. This is achieved with the 3ACES analytics engine that allows for an iterative data analysis process to take place, based on multiple advanced Machine Learning (ML) algorithms that make the most out of the existing data. Finally, the insights produced are presented through an advanced visualization interface, that constitutes the 3ACES business intelligence provider aiming to assist the tech-savvy business user in taking action into strategic and/or business decisions - or simply identify malfunctions in existing processes.

2.2.2 *Technologies used by the tool*

3ACES uses its analytics engine which allows for an iterative data analysis process to take place, based on multiple advanced Machine Learning (ML) algorithms, which make the most out of the existing data to achieve self-service analytics. To elaborate, 3ACES and the sub-module Data Fusion Bus (DFB) is delivered via Kubernetes and Dockers, utilizing technologies like Apache Kafka, Java Spring Boot framework, Laravel, and supports extension by adding other MQ protocols for specific use cases.

2.2.3 *Background of the tool*

3ACES is an in-house developed tool. It is developed based on the Apache Spark framework and Apache Kafka streaming platform.

2.2.4 *Development/deployment timeline in the project*

3ACES comes hand in hand with Security infusion as the main tools deployed in the first MVP and the final integrated solution. Therefore, it will be presented within M8 and progressively until the end of the project.

2.2.5 *Link to demonstrators (in WP6)*

Since WP6 builds directly upon the outputs of WP5, 3ACEs will definitely take part in most demonstrators.

2.2.6 Expected TRL level of the tool at the end of the project and prospective use after COLLABS

3ACEs will reach TRL level 6-7 and expected to be used commercially as an individual solution or within the overall integrated solution which is developed within COLLABS.

2.3 IoT Secure wireless fingerprinting (UNSPMF)

2.3.1 Short description of tool

The component allows for collecting fingerprints from static indoor end-user IoT devices, in order to learn expected behaviour of IoT devices and recognize the situations in which anomalous signals are sent by these devices; it functions in communication and with the help of the ML structured (non)convex optimization and graphical models-based tools component. Fingerprints are used for strong physical layer authentication and they do not rely on the usual identification information transmitted by the IoT device in the data packets/headers (e.g., MAC address or IP address). Fingerprints typically represent some specific features which characterize a particular IoT device and distinguish it from other IoT devices even if they are placed in proximal locations. The major signals used as the device fingerprints are based on the specific features of the stochastic wireless channel (multipath propagation environment) or unique imperfections of the IoT device transmitter hardware.

2.3.2 Technologies used by the tool: Machine Learning, rule-based (e.g. expert system), neural networks,...

Wireless fingerprints are collected using custom-designed or commercial wireless IoT devices that are based on three different technologies: 1) mobile cellular NB-IoT devices, 2) low-power Wi-Fi devices based on IEEE 802.11ah Wi-Fi IoT standard, and 3) standard high-throughput IEEE 802.11ac Wi-Fi devices.

2.3.3 Background of the tool

The tool is based on hardware (IoT device) and software (ML algorithm) that run on the device. The initial platform is developed within the C4IIoT project and is based on NB-IoT technology and anomaly detection algorithms that do not process device fingerprints but only device data coming from the sensors.

2.3.4 Development/deployment timeline in the project

Initial functionalities will be ready for the M12 MVP.

To be augmented with further ML/DL models and privacy preserving techniques and tested and evaluated using real-world data collected within the project.

2.3.5 Link to demonstrators (in WP6): which demonstrator will use it

The described component is fully functional and integrated with the ML structured (non)convex optimization and graphical models-based tools component. However, the two-component system whose initial version we developed is not integrated with the rest of the system within the MVP. This is because the integration requirements were agreed in a later stage and contained demanding changes to the component shown, so it was decided to integrate it with the rest of the system post-MVP.

2.3.6 Expected TRL level of the tool at the end of the project and prospective use after Collabs

TRL level 5 or 6.

2.4 ML structured (non)convex optimization and graphical models-based tools (UNSPMF)

2.4.1 Short description of tool

The component is organized around a framework consisting of Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) models that enable the analysis of behavior of multiple IoT devices. For instance, data collected from, IoT secure wireless fingerprinting components can be fed to this component.

Modules of this component implement models for anomaly detection (AD) and classification that can be applied to fingerprint data, which include: unsupervised outlier detection based on one-class support vector machines (SVM), isolation forests, local outlier factor (LOF), angle-based outlier detection (ABOD), k-nearest neighbours (kNN) and others, as well as supervised methods based on SVMs, random forests, naive Bayes and deep neural networks. All these models can be trained in a supervised or unsupervised way (depending on the availability of labels in collected fingerprint data) to detect anomalous device behaviour and/or identify individual devices based on their fingerprints.

2.4.2 Technology/ies used by the tool

The component includes implementation of unsupervised and supervised ML methods both from the “classical” realm (SVMs, naive Bayes, etc.), as well as Deep Learning methods. This is achieved through the use of several external libraries like: scikit-learn, PyOD, and Tensorflow.

2.4.3 Background of the tool

The tool is based on pre-existing tools or prototypes developed in-house.

2.4.4 Development/deployment timeline in the project

Initial functionalities will be ready for the M12 MVP.

To be augmented with further ML/DL models and privacy preserving techniques and tested and evaluated using real-world data is collected within the project.

2.4.5 *Link to demonstrators (in WP6)*

The described component is fully functional and integrated with the IoT Secure wireless fingerprinting component. However, the two-component system whose initial version we developed is not integrated with the rest of the system within the MVP. This is because the integration requirements were agreed in a later stage and contained demanding changes to the component shown, so it was decided to integrate it with the rest of the system post-MVP.

2.4.6 *Expected TRL level of the tool at the end of the project and prospective use after Collabs*

TRL level 5 or 6.

3. Questionnaire on Ethics

The questionnaire is partitioned into two parts, namely 1) the perspective of the AI tools providers, and 2) the perspective of the AI tools users.

3.1 Assessment by AI tools providers

This section gives the perspective of the AI tools providers, namely partners UNSPMF, HUA and ITML.

3.1.1 Human agency and oversight

Section	Subsection	Question	Sub-question	UNSPMF	HUA	ITML
1.1 Human agency and oversight						
	Fundamental rights					
		Did you carry out a fundamental rights impact assessment where there could be a negative impact on fundamental rights? Did you identify and document potential trade-offs made between the different principles and rights?		No, we do not expect our component to process any personal information.	No, because the ML model does not process personal data.	No, we don't expect to process personal data as a part of cyberthreats and possible vulnerabilities handling in a network.

3.1.2 *Technical robustness and safety*

3.1.3 *Privacy and data governance*

None.

3.1.4 *Transparency*

Section	Subsection	Question	Sub-question	UNSPMF	HUA	ITML
1.4 Transparency						
	<i>Traceability</i>					
		Did you establish measures that can ensure traceability? This could entail documenting the following methods		Yes, it is planned to log all AI software components' activities heavily.	No, it was out of their scope of our work	Yes. the component is responsible for tracing all logs and events to ensure data integrity.
			Methods used for designing and developing the algorithmic system:	Yes, will be documented in detail within project deliverables.		Yes, documentation will be provided.
			. Rule-based AI systems: the method of programming or how the model was built;	N/A		n/a
			. Learning-based AI systems; the method of training the algorithm, including which input data was gathered and selected, and how this occurred	Yes, it will be documented in detail within project deliverables.		N/A
			Methods used to test and validate the algorithmic system:	No, it might be out of our scope within this project		N/A
			. Rule-based AI systems; the scenarios or cases used in order to test and validate;	N/A		N/A
			. Learning-based model: information about the data used to test and validate.	Yes, datasets created by us will be described in details with the project deliverables.		N/A
			Outcomes of the algorithmic system:	Yes		Yes
			. The outcomes of or decisions taken by the algorithm, as well as potential other decisions that would result from	No		N/A

3.1.5 Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

Section	Subsection	Question	Sub-question	UNSPMF	HUA	ITML					
1.5 Diversity, Non-discrimination and fairness	Accessibility and universal design			No, out of our scope in this project - No, it was out of ther scope of	our work	N/A					
				Did you ensure that the AI system accommodates a wide range of individual preferences and abilities?		the whole section 1.5	No				
				Did you assess whether the AI system usable by those with special needs or disabilities or those at risk of exclusion? How was this designed into the system and how is it verified?			No				
				Did you ensure that information about the AI system is accessible also to users of assistive techNologies?		No	No				
				Did you involve or consult this community during the development phase of the AI system?		No	No				
				Did you take the impact of your AI system on the potential user audience into account?		No	No, it was out of ther scope of our work	No, was Not required for			
				Did you assess whether the team involved in building the AI system is representative of your target user audience? Is it representative of the wider population, considering also of other groups who might tangentially be impacted?		No		COLLABS N/A			
				Did you assess whether there could be persons or groups who might be disproportionately affected by negative implications?		No		N/A			
				Did you get feedback from other teams or groups that represent different backgrounds and experiences?		No		N/A			
				Stakeholder participation							
				Did you consider a mechanism to include the participation of different stakeholders in the AI system's development and use?			Yes, use case scenarios have been worked out, described in project deliverables	The AI system has a sigle user. The data owner	No		
				Did you pave the way for the introduction of the AI system in your organisation by informing and involving impacted workers and their representatives in advance?			Yes, we plan to inherit and augment and further develop the component within other activities in our organization	The AI system does Not affect any workers	No, it does Not affect workers within our organization		

3.1.6. Societal and environmental well-being

None.

3.1.7. Accountability						
Section	Subsection	Question	Sub-question	UNSPMF	HUA	ITML
1.7. Accountability						
	<i>Auditability</i>					
		Did you establish mechanisms that facilitate the system's auditability, such as ensuring traceability and logging of the AI system's processes and outcomes?		Yes, included in the component itself	No, it was out of ther scope of our work	Yes, it is one of the component's features
		Did you ensure, in applications affecting fundamental rights (including safety-critical applications) that the AI system can be audited independently?		No, sound like we do not cover this part either	No, it was out of ther scope of our work	N/A in the framework of COLLABS

3.2 Assessment by AI tools users

This section gives the perspective of the AI tools users, namely partners REN, ALES and PCL.

3.2.1 Human agency and oversight

Section	Sub-section	Question	Sub-question	REN replies	ALES replies	PCL replies
1.1 Human agency and oversight						
	Fundamental rights					
		Does the AI system interact with decisions by human (end) users (e.g. recommended actions or decisions to take, presenting of options)?		Yes, output of AI systems will be used by humans to analyze some events like anomalies, malware ... And to help taking actions and decisions.	Yes, we envision possible AI to Human interactions	Yes, the output of the AI will be used by IT professionals. In particular conclusions about data (stationary and in transit) and (malware) anomalies might drive actions or decisions
			Could the AI system affect human autonomy by interfering with the (end) user's decision-making process in an unintended way?	No, output of AI system is only an information, additional information to take a decision. AI system will not interfere in the organizational process, human driven.	Yes, a possible AI to human interaction can lead to a wrong decision by the human (e.g. AI evaluated cybersecurity risk can lead to human decisions)	No, the output of the AI will be used to inform the IT professional user. Only in specific scenario's will automated actions by the AI be sanctioned. The representative infrastructure for the COLLABS project further limits potential risk
			Did you consider whether the AI system should communicate to (end) users that a decision content, advice or outcome is the result of an algorithmic decision?	The output of the AI system will be analyzed by IT professional that will be trained and informed regarding AI system that has produced the information.	Yes, we envision AI that only provides suggestions and not autonomous decisions. Anyway the user will be aware that such insight comes from an AI	The output of the AI will only be represented to IT professionals. We don't feel it's necessary to add such disclaimers for these types of users
			In case of a chat bot or other conversational system, are the human end users made aware that they are interacting with a non-human agent?	This kind of service will not be used in COLLABS.	No, we don't envision presence of a conversational system	Not applicable
	Human agency					
		Is the AI system implemented in work and labour process? If so, did you consider the task allocation between the AI system and humans for meaningful interactions and appropriate human oversight and control?		Yes, AI system will only provide information. It is not planned to put in place automated actions managed by AI system.	Yes, we envision a possible AI to be supervised by humans all the time (hence only provides suggestions, not decisions)	Yes, the AI system will utilize data flows coming from machines. Only in specific scenario's will automated actions by the AI be sanctioned. The representative infrastructure for the COLLABS project further limits potential risk
			Does the AI system enhance or augment human capabilities?	Yes, it helps the processing of a huge amount of data (correlation, sorting ...)	Yes, the AI should provide insight in otherwise unused data (e.g. passive network analysis)	Yes, in the sense that automated data inspection and anomaly detection fall outside the scope of human capabilities
			Did you take safeguards to prevent overconfidence or overreliance on the AI system for work processes?	Yes, output of AI system is only information and will not generate automatic actions.	Since AI are only used for data mining and suggestion we use humans as decision takers and therefore as safeguards	Yes, a false-positive result might lead to wasted research effort which is an acceptable risk. Only in certain sanctioned use cases a false-positive result might lead to an acceptable outage in our representative infrastructure

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Human oversight				
	Did you consider the appropriate level of human control for the particular AI system and use case?	Yes IT specialist will analyze output of AI system.	Since AI are only used for data mining and suggestion we use humans as decision takers and therefore as safeguards	Yes
	Can you describe the level of human control or involvement?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Human makes all the decision/actions, AI does only provide suggestions	The output of the AI will be used to inform the IT professional user. Only in specific scenario's will automated actions by the AI be sanctioned.
	Who is the "human in control" and what are the moments or tools for human intervention?	Too early for COLLABS project.	A cybersecurity specialist will take action based on informations (that might come from AI)	The Philips PCL project member. Specific tools for intervention are yet to be developed by technology providers, it's important that the reasons for AI conclusions are clear. Moments for intervention take place during confirmed false-positive results
	Did you put in place mechanisms and measures to ensure human control or oversight?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Human makes all the decision/actions, AI does only provide suggestions	Yes, the output of the AI will be used to inform the IT professional user. Only in specific scenario's will automated actions by the AI be sanctioned.
	Did you take any measures to enable audit and to remedy issues related to governing AI autonomy?	Not applicable	All the AI results are suggestion and therefore auditable. The AI system can always be updated/reset if needed	Yes, deliverable 1.2 states a number of requirements relating to traceability and audibility
	Is there a self-learning or autonomous AI system or use case? If so, did you put in place more specific mechanisms of control and oversight?	Yes, specifically regarding data and anomaly detection. No further specific mechanisms or controls are used.	All the AI results are suggestion and therefore auditable. The AI system can always be updated/reset if needed	Yes, specifically regarding data and anomaly detection. No further specific mechanisms or controls are used.
	Which detection and response mechanisms did you establish to assess whether something could go wrong?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Human makes all the decision/actions, AI does only provide suggestions	Conclusions regarding data and anomalies will have to be verified by expert analysis and technical benchmarks yet to be established in cooperation with the technology provider(s)
	Did you ensure a stop button or procedure to safely abort an operation where needed? Does this procedure abort the process entirely, in part, or delegate control to a human?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Yes, we envision a safety abort mechanism for the AI	No, This is not necessary in our use cases. The representative infrastructure for the COLLABS project limits potential risk to an acceptable level

3.2.2 Technical robustness and safety

Section	Sub-section	Question	Sub-question	REN replies	ALES replies	PCL replies
1,2 Technical robustness and safety	<i>Fallback plan and general safety</i>					
		Did you ensure that your system has a sufficient fallback plan if it encounters adversarial attacks or other unexpected situations (for example technical switching procedures or asking for a human operator before proceeding)?		Not necessary. AI system provide information but will not interfere with operations.	Human makes all the decision/actions, AI does only provide suggestions	No, this is not necessary in our use cases. The representative infrastructure for the COLLABS project limits potential risk to an acceptable level
		Did you consider the level of risk raised by the AI system in this specific use case?		Not applicable	Yes, since AI is just producing insight we don't foresee a high level of risk	Yes, this is one of the reasons we utilize a representative infrastructure which limits potential risk to an acceptable level
			Did you put any process in place to measure and assess risks and safety?	Not applicable	Yes, we perform security risk assessment on our systems	No, there are no ongoing processes in place. Risks and potential safety impact was thoroughly discussed with the consortium and has led to the current representative infrastructure
			Did you provide the necessary information in case of a risk for human physical integrity?	Not applicable	No, there is no such risk	Not applicable
			Did you consider an insurance policy to deal with potential damage from the AI system?	Not applicable	No, there is no such risk	Not applicable
			Did you identify potential safety risks of (other) foreseeable uses of the technology, including accidental or malicious misuse? Is there a plan to mitigate or manage these risks?	Not applicable	No, there is no such risk	Not applicable
		Did you assess whether there is a probable chance that the AI system may cause damage or harm to users or third parties? Did you assess the likelihood, potential damage, impacted audience and severity?		Yes, not applicable.	Yes, we assessed there is no such risk	Yes, risks and potential safety impact was thoroughly discussed with the consortium and has led to the current representative infrastructure
			Did you consider the liability and consumer protection rules, and take them into account?	Not applicable	No, there is no such risk	Not applicable
			Did you consider the potential impact or safety risk to the environment or to animals?	Not applicable	No, there is no such risk	Not applicable
			Did your risk analysis include whether security or network problems such as cybersecurity hazards could pose safety risks or damage due to unintentional behaviour of the AI system?	Yes	No, there is no such risk	Yes

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	Did you estimate the likely impact of a failure of your AI system when it provides wrong results, becomes unavailable, or provides societally unacceptable results (for example discrimination)?	Yes, risks have been evaluated. And considered acceptable.	Yes, we have a human based decision system therefore this mitigate those risks	Yes, as we are dealing with machine data and are intending to utilize these systems to provide additional capabilities this risk is acceptable.
	Did you define thresholds and did you put governance procedures in place to trigger alternative/fallback plans?	Too early for COLLABS project.	No, it is not needed	No, it is too early in the project to define such thresholds. Specific governance is not necessary
	Did you define and test fallback plans?	No	No, it is not needed	No
	Accuracy			
	Did you assess what level and definition of accuracy would be required in the context of the AI system and use case?	Work in progress. KPI definition.	Yes, we plan to have an accuracy level defined before accepting data from the AI as potential suggestions	Yes, this is defined in project KPI-2.2 and KPI -2.4
	Did you assess how accuracy is measured and assured?	No, to define.	Yes, we plan to have an accuracy level defined before accepting data from the AI as potential suggestions	Yes, see deliverable D1.2 Section 3, subsection C.i
	Did you put in place measures to ensure that the data used is comprehensive and up to date?	Yes, AI system will be trained with production data.	We foresee AI working on live data	Yes, the ML models will be trained using ongoing production data
	Did you put in place measures in place to assess whether there is a need for additional data, for example to improve accuracy or to eliminate bias?	No, to analyze	We foresee AI to get a first training on controlled datasets before running live on the real-life scenario	No, it's too early in the project for this. Discussions regarding data classification and anomaly detection still need to take place for the MVP
	Did you verify what harm would be caused if the AI system makes inaccurate predictions?	Yes, risk has been evaluated. No risk, no automatic actions related to production.	Yes, we assessed there is no such risk	Yes, a false-positive result might lead to wasted research effort which is an acceptable risk. Only in certain sanctioned use cases a false-positive result might lead to an acceptable outage in our representative infrastructure
	Did you put in place ways to measure whether your system is making an unacceptable amount of inaccurate predictions?	No	Yes, we plan to have a system to collect human feedbacks on wrong suggestions	No, conclusions regarding data and anomalies will have to be verified by expert analysis and technical benchmarks yet to be established in cooperation with the technology provider(s)
	Did you put in place a series of steps to increase the system's accuracy?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Yes, self-learning and human feedbacks can be used for AI self improvement	No, it's too early in the project for this. Discussions regarding data classification and anomaly detection still need to take place for the MVP
	Reliability and reproducibility			
	Did you put in place a strategy to monitor and test if the AI system is meeting the goals, purposes and intended applications?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Yes, we plan to have a system to collect human feedbacks on wrong suggestions (and use this as failure rate measurement)	The AI goals are defined in project KPI-2.2 and KPI -2.4. Deliverable D1.2 Section 3, subsection C.i defines the desired outcome and means of validation from PCL perspective
	Did you test whether specific contexts or particular conditions need to be taken into account to ensure reproducibility?		Yes, we envision a specific environment (reference architecture with specific services)	No, it's too early in the project for this.
	Did you put in place verification methods to measure and ensure different aspects of the system's reliability and reproducibility?		Yes, we plan to develop and test verification systems for AI	No, conclusions regarding data and anomalies will have to be verified by expert analysis and technical benchmarks yet to be established in cooperation with the technology provider(s)
	Did you put in place processes to describe when an AI system fails in certain types of settings?		Yes, when a user signals an error some data should be gathered with the results to provide context	No, it's too early in the project for this.
	Did you clearly document and operationalise these processes for the testing and verification of the reliability of AI systems?		Not yet	No, it's too early in the project for this.
	Did you establish mechanisms of communication to assure (end-users of the system's reliability?		No, since there is no autonomous decision we do not plan on this	Not applicable

3.2.3 Privacy and data governance

Section	Sub-section	Question	Sub-question	REN replies	ALES replies	PCL replies
1.3 Privacy and data governance						
<i>Respect for privacy and data Protection</i>						
		Depending on the use case, did you establish a mechanism allowing others to flag issues related to privacy or data protection in the AI system's processes of data collection (for training and operation) and data processing?		Not applicable	We don't foresee any AI to collect and store privacy related data	Not applicable
		Did you assess the type and scope of data in your data sets (for example whether they contain personal data)?		Yes, no personal data, only production data.	We don't foresee any AI to collect and store privacy related data	Yes, the intended data does not include personal data
		Did you consider ways to develop the AI system or train the model without or with minimal use of potentially sensitive or personal data?		Not applicable	Yes, we plan to store the minimum amount of data and use only anonymized data	Not applicable
		Did you consider ways to develop the AI system or train the model without or with minimal use of potentially sensitive or personal data?		Not applicable	Yes, we plan to store the minimum amount of data and use only anonymized data	Not applicable
		Did you take measures to enhance privacy, such as via encryption, anonymisation and aggregation?		Not applicable	Yes, we plan to store the minimum amount of data and use only anonymized data	Not applicable
		Where a Data Privacy Officer (DPO) exists, did you involve this person at an early stage in the process?		Not applicable	We don't have a DPO	Not applicable
<i>Quality and integrity of data</i>						
		Did you align your system with relevant standards (for example ISO, IEEE) or widely adopted protocols for daily data management and governance?		Yes, security requirements are mapped to IEC 62443-3-3 and NIST SP 800-1721	The COLLABS framework plans to align with NIST and ISA security regulations	Yes, security requirements are mapped to IEC 62443-3-3 and NIST SP 800-1721
		Did you establish oversight mechanisms for data collection, storage, processing and use?		Yes	Yes, we plan to have a structured analysis on any data related activities performed by AI	No
		Did you assess the extent to which you are in control of the quality of the external data sources used?		No. Too early in the project.	Yes, we are not in control of the external data source and therefore all the sources should be validated by experts	No, it's too early in the project for this. External data sources might be used by solutions from technology providers but this is unclear at this time
		Did you put in place processes to ensure the quality and integrity of your data? Did you consider other processes? How are you verifying that your data sets have not been compromised or hacked?		Use of security protocols to ensure integrity.	Yes, COLLABS provides systems to ensure data integrity. We also plan to keep the data we store at an inimum (the less the better)	Yes, quality and integrity of the data falls outside of COLLABS' scope. Detecting anomalies in data sets is part of this COLLABS' goals
<i>Access to data</i>						
		What protocols, processes and procedures did you follow to manage and ensure proper data governance?		Corporate procedures (ISSP)	We plan to follow NIST SP800-171 and ISA/IEC 62443 as guidelines	Existing IT policies including the principle of least privilege are followed
			Did you assess who can access users' data, and under what circumstances?	Yes	We do not plan to gather user data in AI context	Yes, principle of least privilege limits access to only those necessary. We are not dealing with user data
			Did you ensure that these persons are qualified and required to access the data, and that they have the necessary competences to understand the details of data protection policy?	Yes	We do not plan to gather user data in AI context	Yes
			Did you ensure an oversight mechanism to log when, where, how, by whom and for what purpose data was accessed?	Yes	We do not plan to gather user data in AI context	Yes, this is handled through CSR-03, CSR-07, CSR-08, CSR-09

3.2.4.1 Transparency

Section	Sub-section	Question	Sub-question	REN replies	ALES replies	PCL replies
1.4 Transparency						
	<i>Explainability</i>					
		Did you assess:				
			to what extent the decisions and hence the outcome made by the AI system can be understood?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Yes, we envision a study on how to present the AI results properly	No, it's too early in the project for this.
			to what degree the system's decision influences the organization's decision-making processes?	No, to analyze.	The AI provide cybersecurity insights, therefore they are bound to influence cybersecurity decisions (which should never affect the industrial process)	Yes, the output of the AI will be used by IT professionals. In particular conclusions about data (stationary and in transit) and (malware) anomalies might drive actions or decisions
			why this particular system was deployed in this specific area?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Enhance cybersecurity	No, it's too early in the project for this.
			what the system's business model is (for example, how does it create value for the organization)?	See grant agreement.	This helps protecting intellectual properties and to avoid operation disruption by an attacker	Yes, this is described in the Grant Agreement and in Deliverable 1.2 and 1.3
		Did you ensure an explanation as to why the system took a certain choice resulting in a certain outcome that all users can understand?		Too early for COLLABS project.	Yes, we envision a study on how to present the AI results properly	No, it's too early in the project for this.
		Did you design the AI system with interpretability in mind from the start?		Not applicable. Not the AI system designer.	Yes, we envision a study on how to present the AI results properly	Not applicable - We are not designing the AI System
			Did you research and try to use the simplest and most interpretable model possible for the application in question?			Not applicable
			Did you assess whether you can analyze your training and testing data? Can you change and update this over time?		Yes, we expect to have full control over training/testing datasets	Not applicable
			Did you assess whether you can examine interpretability after the model's training and development, or whether you have access to the internal workflow of the model?			Not Applicable
	<i>Communication</i>					
		Did you communicate to (end)-users – through a disclaimer or any other means – that they are interacting with an AI system and not with another human? Did you label your AI system as such?		No. Not required.	No, but we expect to be clear from interface that there is no human behind it	No, the output of the AI will only be represented to IT professionals. We don't feel it's necessary to add such disclaimers for these types of users
		Did you establish mechanisms to inform (end)-users on the reasons and criteria behind the AI system's outcomes?		Too early for COLLABS project.	Yes, we envision a study on how to present the AI results properly	No, the output of the AI will only be represented to IT professionals. We don't feel it's necessary to add such disclaimers for these types of users
			Did you communicate this clearly and intelligibly to the intended audience?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Yes, we envision a study on how to present the AI results properly	The intended audience is aware
			Did you establish processes that consider users' feedback and use this to adapt the system?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Yes, we envision a system of feedbacks from users on AI results	No, it's too early in the project for this.
			Did you communicate around potential or perceived risks, such as bias?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Yes, we plan to strongly highlight that the AI is just providing suggestions and not decisions	Not applicable
			Depending on the use case, did you consider communication and transparency towards other audiences, third parties or the general public?	Too early for COLLABS project.	No	Not applicable

D1.4 - Applicability of the Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI to the COLLABS approach

	Did you clarify the purpose of the AI system and who or what may benefit from the product/service?	Yes in the use cases description.	Yes, we envision a study on how to present the AI results properly	We believe this is described sufficiently in the WP1 deliverables
	Did you specify usage scenarios for the product and clearly communicate these to ensure that it is understandable and appropriate for the intended audience?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Yes, we envision a study on how to present the AI results properly	The intended audience is aware
	Depending on the use case, did you think about human psychology and potential limitations, such as risk of confusion, confirmation bias or cognitive fatigue?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Yes, we foresee a possible confirmation bias (humans always confirming AI suggestions) and therefore we plan to highlight user responsibility whenever a suggestion is confirmed	Not applicable
	Did you clearly communicate characteristics, limitations and potential shortcomings of the AI system?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Yes, the AI results should be presented as "possible" not "certain"	No, it's too early in the project for this.
	In case of the system's development: to whoever is deploying it into a product or service?	Too early for COLLABS project.	No, this is a prototype and therefore developer, users and deployer are mainly the same people	No, it's too early in the project for this.
	In case of the system's deployment: to the (end)-user or consumer?	Too early for COLLABS project.	No, this is a prototype and therefore developer, users and deployer are mainly the same people	No, it's too early in the project for this.
Unfair bias avoidance				
	Did you establish a strategy or a set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing unfair bias in the AI system, both regarding the use of input data as well as for the algorithm design?	Too early for COLLABS project.	No, we just use AI algorithms from the tech providers, therefore we assume this is planned by them	Not applicable for our datasets
	Did you assess and acknowledge the possible limitations stemming from the composition of the used data sets?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Yes, we acknowledged the limitation of the data since we will not feed it with real life data but just with simulations of it	No, it's too early in the project for this.
	Did you consider diversity and representativeness of users in the data? Did you test for specific populations or problematic use cases?	Not applicable	Yes, we acknowledged the limitation of the data since we will not feed it with real life data but just with simulations of it	Not applicable
	Did you research and use available technical tools to improve your understanding of the data, model and performance?	Not applicable	No, we just use AI algorithms from the tech providers, therefore we assume this is planned by them	Not applicable
	Did you put in place processes to test and monitor for potential biases during the development, deployment and use phase of the system?	Not applicable	No, we just use AI algorithms from the tech providers, therefore we assume this is planned by them	Not applicable
	Depending on the use case, did you ensure a mechanism that allows others to flag issues related to bias, discrimination or poor performance of the AI system?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Not applicable	No, it's too early in the project for this.
	Did you establish clear steps and ways of communicating on how and to whom such issues can be raised?	Too early for COLLABS project.	Not applicable	No, it's too early in the project for this.
	Did you consider others, potentially indirectly affected by the AI system, in addition to the (end)- users?	No	Not applicable	Not applicable
	Did you assess whether there is any possible decision variability that can occur under the same conditions?	Too early for COLLABS project.	No, we just use AI algorithms from the tech providers, therefore we assume this is planned by them	No, it's too early in the project for this.
	If so, did you consider what the possible causes of this could be?	Too early for COLLABS project.	No, we just use AI algorithms from the tech providers, therefore we assume this is planned by them	No, it's too early in the project for this.
	In case of variability, did you establish a measurement or assessment mechanism of the potential impact of such variability on fundamental rights?	Too early for COLLABS project.	No, we just use AI algorithms from the tech providers, therefore we assume this is planned by them	No, it's too early in the project for this.
	Did you ensure an adequate working definition of "fairness" that you apply in designing AI systems?	Not applicable. Not the AI system designer.	Not applicable	Not applicable - we are not designing the system
	Is your definition commonly used? Did you consider other definitions before choosing this one?	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable
	Did you ensure a quantitative analysis or metrics to measure and test the applied definition of fairness?	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable
	Did you establish mechanisms to ensure fairness in your AI systems? Did you consider other potential mechanisms?	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable

3.2.5 Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

Not applicable.

3.2.6. Societal and environmental well-being

Section	Sub-section	Question	Sub-question	REN replies	ALES replies	PCL replies
1.6. Societal and environmental well-being						
	<i>Sustainable and environmentally friendly AI</i>					
		Did you establish mechanisms to measure the environmental impact of the AI system's development, deployment and use (for example the type of energy used by the data centres)?		No	No, we did not assessed the environmental impact	Not applicable
		Did you ensure measures to reduce the environmental impact of your AI system's life cycle?		No	No	Not applicable
	<i>Social impact</i>					
		In case the AI system interacts directly with humans				Not applicable
			Did you assess whether the AI system encourages humans to develop attachment and empathy towards the system?	Not applicable	No, there is no such risk	Not applicable
			Did you ensure that the AI system clearly signals that its social interaction is simulated and that it has no capacities of "understanding" and "feeling"?	Not applicable	No, there is no such risk	Not applicable
		Did you ensure that the social impacts of the AI system are well understood? For example, did you assess whether there is a risk of job loss or de-skilling of the workforce? What steps have been taken to counteract such risks?		Not applicable	Yes, since AI is just producing insight we don't expect a de-skilling of the workforce	Not applicable
	<i>Society and democracy</i>					
		Did you assess the broader societal impact of the AI system's use beyond the individual (end-)user, such as potentially indirectly affected stakeholders?		Not applicable	Yes, we don't foresee any stakeholder indirectly impacted	Not applicable

3.2.7. Accountability

Section	Sub-section	Question	Sub-question	REN replies	ALES replies	PCL replies
1.7. Accountability						
	<i>Minimising and reporting negative Impact</i>					
		Did you carry out a risk or impact assessment of the AI system, which takes into account different stakeholders that are (in)directly affected?		Too early for COLLABS project.	We don't foresee any stakeholder indirectly impacted	Not formally
		Did you provide training and education to help developing accountability practices?		No	No, we don't plan to provide training/education	No
			Which workers or branches of the team are involved? Does it go beyond the development phase? Do these trainings also teach the potential legal framework applicable to the AI system?	IT professionals	No, we don't plan to provide training/education	IT Professionals
			Did you consider establishing an 'ethical AI review board' or a similar mechanism to discuss overall accountability and ethics practices, including potentially unclear grey areas?	No, don't think necessary	No, we don't plan to establish "ethical AI review board"	No, we don't feel this is necessary
		Did you foresee any kind of external guidance or put in place auditing processes to oversee ethics and accountability, in addition to internal initiatives?		No	No, we don't plan any ethics accountability process	No
		Did you establish processes for third parties (e.g. suppliers, consumers, distributors/vendors) or workers to report potential vulnerabilities, risks or biases in the AI system?		No	No, we don't foresee third party interaction with AI	No
	<i>Documenting trade-offs</i>					
		Did you establish a mechanism to identify relevant interests and values implicated by the AI system and potential trade-offs between them?		No	No, we did not identify trade-offs	No
		How do you decide on such trade-offs? Did you ensure that the trade-off decision was documented?		No	No, we did not identify trade-offs	Not applicable
	<i>Ability to redress</i>					
		Did you establish an adequate set of mechanisms that allows for redress in case of the occurrence of any harm or adverse impact?		No	No, the AI is just providing suggestions, not decision making	No
		Did you put mechanisms in place both to provide information to (end-)users/third parties about opportunities for redress?		No	No, the AI is just providing suggestions, not decision making	No

4. *Conclusions*

As the reader might have noticed whilst reading this deliverable, we can observe a great interest of the researchers in the subject of ethics in AI, and more generally of the ethics of digital technologies. The moral issues of automatic decision-making systems, or AI to put it simply, are numerous. Ongoing research and development of new modalities of machine learning and automatic decision-making will also have their share of new moral consequences. And yet, we have only scratched the surface of a subject with far broader consequences than we imagined at the start.

In terms of perspectives, the deliverable has given a concise view of the use of AI techniques at the end of the first project year. The views expressed by AI tools providers differ from the views of AI tools users due to the in-depth knowledge of AI by the former w.r.t. the later who gave their vision on Ethics. At this stage, many developments are under way in COLLABS and the knowledge expressed here is not definite nor complete. The partners will have a more objective vision of how they use AI tools during later stages of the project, which will consolidate and/or complete their position.

List of Abbreviations

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Translation</i>
<i>ML/DL</i>	<i>Machine Learning/Deep Learning</i>
<i>KPI</i>	<i>Key Performance Indicators</i>
<i>DPO</i>	<i>Data Privacy Officer</i>
<i>E2E</i>	<i>Enterprise To Enterprise</i>
<i>SIEM</i>	<i>Security Information and Events Management</i>
<i>IVT</i>	<i>Interim Visualisation Tool</i>
<i>C4IIoT</i>	<i>Cyber-security for Industrial IoT</i>
<i>MVT</i>	<i>Minimum Viable Product</i>
<i>SVM</i>	<i>Support Vector Machine</i>
<i>ABOD</i>	<i>Angle-Based Outlier Detection</i>

Bibliography

[1] Independent High-level expert group on AI setup by the European Commission. Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. 8th April 2018.